

Large Reactor-Neutrino Mixing Angle Supports a Fourier Approach to the Mass Hierarchy Problem

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The neutrino mass hierarchy problem presents an important open question in particle physics. Two alternate hypotheses describe the mass-ordering of the three neutrino masses: the ‘normal’ hierarchy, $m_1 < m_2 < m_3$; and the ‘inverted’ hierarchy, $m_3 < m_1 < m_2$. We review a method for measuring the neutrino mass hierarchy using Fourier analysis of reactor electron antineutrino disappearance oscillations. We present theoretical curves describing the expected response of a 10 kt scintillator-doped water-based electron antineutrino detector positioned 50 km away from a 8 GWth nuclear reactor, using updated neutrino oscillation parameters; the experimental consensus around a ‘large’ reactor neutrino mixing angle, $\theta_{13} \approx 0.16 > 0$, supports the viability of our approach. We show a strong mass hierarchy dependence in the *shape* of the Fourier power spectrum, robust under uncertainties on the absolute values of the hierarchy parameters $|\Delta m^2_{ij}|$.

I. INTRODUCTION

Since the discovery that neutrinos have mass, a measurement of the hierarchy of the three known neutrino mass states, ν_1 , ν_2 , and ν_3 , with corresponding masses m_1 , m_2 , and m_3 , has proven elusive. It is known that $m_1 < m_2$, but two alternate hypotheses persist for the relative magnitude of m_3 : the ‘normal’ hierarchy, $m_1 < m_2 < m_3$; and the ‘inverted’ hierarchy, $m_3 < m_1 < m_2$.

In addition to mass, neutrinos carry other properties, one of which is ‘flavor.’ Neutrinos (and antineutrinos) come in three flavors—electron, muon, and tau—referring to the particular flavor of charged lepton they couple to in weak-force interactions mediated by W boson exchange. A neutrino produced by such a process is produced in a state of definite flavor. A neutrino with definite flavor, however, does not have a definite mass, so this definite-flavor neutrino must propagate through space with some specific simultaneous combination, or superposition, of the possible masses m_1 , m_2 , and m_3 . These mass states interfere with one another, so the amount of probability each mass contributes to the overall state of the neutrino varies in time. In the language of quantum mechanics, the complex phase of each definite mass component of the neutrino’s wave function varies in proportion to that mass, so the different mass state amplitudes interfere in their superposition. Since a neutrino with definite flavor is in one *specific* superposition of mass states, as the mass state contributions vary, so too does the neutrino’s flavor oscillate through the possible superpositions of flavor states. Thus, a neutrino produced with some definite flavor may later be detected in a different flavor, an observed phenomenon known as neutrino oscillation.

Neutrino oscillation experiments typically employ the “inverse beta decay” particle interaction to detect definite flavor (electron) antineutrinos. In inverse beta decay, an electron antineutrino and a proton engage in a weak-force interaction, mediated by a W^+ boson, to form the

process:

$$\bar{\nu}_e + p \rightarrow e^+ + n \quad (1)$$

In a neutrino detector, the outgoing positron and neutron are detected by some means, dependent on the detector technology.

Nuclear reactors are intense sources of electron antineutrinos (a definite neutrino flavor state), so reactor antineutrino fluxes are heavily studied for the insights they offer into neutrino oscillations. For an electron antineutrino with energy E (MeV), the probability P_{ee} that it will be detected as an electron antineutrino (i.e., with the same flavor) some distance L (m) away from its source is given by:

$$P_{ee} = 1 - [\cos^4(\theta_{13}) \sin^2(2\theta_{12}) \sin^2(\Delta_{21}) + \cos^2(\theta_{12}) \sin^2(2\theta_{13}) \sin^2(\Delta_{31}) + \sin^2(\theta_{12}) \sin^2(2\theta_{13}) \sin^2(\Delta_{32})] \quad (2)$$

where the “neutrino mixing angles” θ_{ij} quantify the relationships between neutrino mass and flavor states. $\Delta_{ij} \equiv 1.27 \text{ m}^{-1} \text{ MeV}^{-1} c^4 |\Delta m^2_{ji}| L/E$ controls the oscillations with

$$\Delta m^2_{ji} \equiv m_j^2 - m_i^2 \quad (3)$$

denoting the mass-squared difference between ν_i and ν_j within the mass hierarchy, in units of $(\text{eV}/c^2)^2$, where c is the speed of light in vacuum. Thus, the frequency of neutrino oscillations as a function of L/E is totally determined by the neutrino mass hierarchy: explicitly, $|\Delta m^2_{32}| < |\Delta m^2_{31}|$ in the normal hierarchy, while $|\Delta m^2_{31}| < |\Delta m^2_{32}|$ in the inverted hierarchy. This strict relationship between the neutrino masses and the oscillating disappearance and reappearance of electron antineutrinos (1) as a function of L/E presents an experimental opportunity to solve the neutrino mass hierarchy problem by characterizing the oscillation frequencies present in a detected reactor antineutrino flux.

II. METHODS

We simulate a reactor antineutrino flux spectrum as a function of antineutrino energy E , based on the isotopic compositions of the fission cores and their thermal power output. We then simulate the effects of neutrino oscillation over some reactor-detector distance L by equation (2). Finally, we simulate the detection of the surviving electron antineutrino flux based on detector size, composition, and appropriate antineutrino-proton interaction cross sections, relevant to the inverse beta decay signal (1). We convolve the resulting theoretical detection curves with appropriate Gaussian energy smearing functions. Finally, we transform the energy spectrum into a spectrum in L/E , where the underlying disappearance signal is a simple superposition of three sine-squareds (2).

To separate out the mass hierarchy parameters Δm_{ij}^2 present in the detector response, we apply a Fourier transform into $|\Delta m^2|$ space. Here the relative powers of the oscillation frequencies are clearly distinguished, assuming the original detector response contains a sufficient number of clear oscillation cycles at the frequencies of interest. By equation (2), the number of cycles present in a given energy domain, as well as the total neutrino event rate, is highly dependent on the reactor-detector distance, or ‘baseline.’

Note that the *values* of Δm_{31}^2 or Δm_{32}^2 need not be accurately measured to distinguish between mass hierarchies. As shown in Figure 4, the shape alone of the $|\Delta m^2|$ transform is sufficient to determine the mass hierarchy present in a given L/E spectrum. To emphasize this distinction, we align and normalize to one the power of the $|\Delta m_{31}^2|$ peaks between spectra.

As previous authors have reported [1], the strength of such an approach is highly dependent on the magnitude of the mixing angle θ_{13} . The power of the hierarchy-dependent spectral geometry shown in Figure 4 grows proportionally with the squared amplitude of the last two terms in equation (2). Specifically, the common factor $\sin^2(2\theta_{13})$ controls the power of the mass hierarchy dependence, so that $\theta_{13} = \pi/2$ maximizes the hierarchy-sensitive oscillations, while $\theta_{13} = 0$ eliminates them entirely. Current measurements have quelled speculation that $\theta_{13} \simeq 0$, with modern best fits [2] placing $\theta_{13} \approx 0.16$, lending considerable credibility to a frequency-domain approach to the mass hierarchy problem.

Previous authors have statistically validated the sensitivity of electron antineutrino disappearance oscillation experiments to the neutrino mass hierarchy [1]. A detailed statistical analysis of the updated approach demonstrated in this paper is underway, in which we employ rejection sampling on the L/E spectrum, varying the number of accepted datapoints in accordance with Poisson statistical fluctuations. We then attempt to reconstruct the hierarchy present in the simulated data by a test statistic, comparing the normalized $|\Delta m^2|$ reconstructed power spectrum with the peak-aligned and normalized expected spectra for both hierarchy cases.

III. RESULTS

In this paper, we present theoretical curves characterizing a best-case, but certainly feasible, experiment to clearly demonstrate the viability of our technique in light of modern θ_{13} measurements. We model the electron antineutrino output of an 8 GWth reactor complex [3], propagate this across a 50 km baseline, and simulate detection in 10 kt of scintillator-doped water with $\sigma_E/E = 3.5\%/\sqrt{E_{\text{visible}}/\text{MeV}}$ energy resolution. E_{visible} is the energy visible to our detector: the energy of the positron generated by process (1), less than the incident neutrino energy by the amount of mass energy required to convert a proton into a neutron, and by kinetic energy left on that neutron. Henceforth, $3.5\%/\sqrt{E/\text{MeV}}$ denotes $3.5\%/\sqrt{E_{\text{visible}}/\text{MeV}}$.

We employ a reactor-detector distance of 50 km to optimize the electron antineutrino flux into the detector[1]. The reactor antineutrino flux spectrum peaks around 3.6 MeV, so a baseline near 50 km maximizes the low frequency Δ_{21} oscillations by setting the argument of that sine-squared (2) to $\pi/2$. By placing our detector near a low-frequency maximum, we nearly maximize the incident electron antineutrino flux, decreasing the time to accumulate a statistically sufficient sample of neutrino energy measurements, and increasing the signal-to-background ratio (though we do not specify backgrounds in this simulation).

We use experimentally determined best fit neutrino oscillation parameters:

TABLE I. Neutrino Oscillation Parameters [2]

parameter	best fit (normal, inverted)
$\Delta m_{21}^2 (10^{-5} \text{ eV}^2/c^4)$	7.62
$ \Delta m_{31}^2 (10^{-3} \text{ eV}^2/c^4)$	2.55, 2.55
$\sin^2 \theta_{12}$	0.320
$\sin^2 \theta_{13}$	0.0246, 0.0250

Only one value is listed for hierarchy-independent parameters.

Neutrino oscillations can be seen directly in the detected antineutrino energy spectrum (Figure 1), but distinct oscillation frequencies (1) only become clear when viewing detector response plotted as a function of L/E (Figure 2), where a regular period emerges in the high frequency oscillations.

The $|\Delta m^2|$ transform separates out the three oscillation frequencies present in the detector signal, corresponding to the three sine-squareds of the oscillating electron antineutrino survival probability (1). Each hierarchy parameter Δm_{ij}^2 contributes to the distribution of power in the transformed L/E spectrum (Figure 3), with the lower-amplitude Δm_{32}^2 appearing as a shoulder on the prominent $|\Delta m_{31}^2|$ peak.

FIG. 1. Detection rate vs. antineutrino energy for normal (solid blue) and inverted (dashed orange) mass hierarchies. 80 GW·kt·yr exposure, 50 km from the source reactor. $3.5\%/\sqrt{E/\text{MeV}}$ Gaussian energy smearing applied.

FIG. 3. Fourier $|\Delta m^2|$ power spectrum of the unsmeared L/E detection curve, plotting unit-less power on a logarithmic scale. The Δm_{31}^2 peak is clearly visible, and we normalize its power contribution to one. Normal hierarchy appears in solid blue, inverted in dashed orange.

FIG. 2. Detection rate vs. flight distance (50 km) over antineutrino energy for normal (solid blue) and inverted (dashed orange) mass hierarchies. 80 GW·kt·yr exposure. $3.5\%/\sqrt{E/\text{MeV}}$ Gaussian energy smearing applied.

Measurement of the values Δm_{31}^2 and Δm_{32}^2 poses a substantial experimental challenge. However, with a sufficient number of measured oscillation cycles (i.e., with a sufficiently long reactor-detector baseline) the shape of the $|\Delta m^2|$ spectrum around the $|\Delta m_{31}^2|$ peak is sufficiently differentiated between hierarchies to distinguish between them. This dependence arises from the *relative* parameter magnitudes $|\Delta m_{32}^2| < |\Delta m_{31}^2|$ in the normal hierarchy, and $|\Delta m_{31}^2| < |\Delta m_{32}^2|$ in the inverted hierarchy, even if the $|\Delta m^2|$ value around which the features appear is experimentally uncertain. We highlight this in Figure 4 (perfect energy resolution) and Figure 5 ($3.5\%/\sqrt{E/\text{MeV}}$ energy resolution), where the hierarchy-sensitive $|\Delta m^2|$ region is plotted on offset axes, aligning normalized $|\Delta m_{31}^2|$ peaks between hierarchies. This presentation suggests an analysis focused on identifying the Fourier geometry present in experimental data, rather than attempting to resolve $|\Delta m^2|$ peak values.

FIG. 4. Detailed view of the hierarchy-sensitive region in the $|\Delta m^2|$ power spectrum of the unsmeared signal, with Δm_{31}^2 peaks aligned and normalized to one to emphasize the shape distinction between hierarchies.

FIG. 5. Same view as Figure 4, with $3.5\%/\sqrt{E/\text{MeV}}$ Gaussian energy smearing applied to the underlying signal.

IV. CONCLUSION

Previous papers [1] have cautioned that the $\sin^2(2\theta_{13})$ coefficients in equation (2) might critically limit our ability to distinguish between the relevant peak geometries in $|\Delta m^2|$ space. For some time, strong speculation that $\theta_{13} \simeq 0$ cast doubt on the presence of any significant information on the relative mass of ν_3 in neutrino oscillation signals. Now, a strong experimental consensus [2] exists for large θ_{13} , reflected in the best-fit value we use in our simulations (Table I). Using these new findings, we have demonstrated the presence of a significant, realistically observable, mass hierarchy dependence in the shape of the Fourier power spectrum of electron antineutrino oscillation signals detected 50 km away from a fission reactor, sufficient to address the neutrino mass hierarchy problem.

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